

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Titanium(IV) with *N-m-Tolyl-p-Methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid*

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The complex formation studies of Ti(IV)-*N-m-tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA) system revealed that titanium forms a 1 : 2 complex (Ti(IV) : TMBHA) with TMBHA. The nature of the extractable species has been shown to be TiOCIR.HR under present experimental conditions. The stepwise conditional stability constants are found to be $\log k_1 = 3.67$ and $\log k_2 = 3.32$ by Yatsimirskii's method and $\log k_1 = 3.54$ and $\log k_2 = 3.20$ by Leden's method. Besides this, TMBHA has been employed for the microdetermination of titanium and the results showed that Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 1.0-8.0 μg Ti(IV) per ml of chloroform at 330 nm. Titanium can be separated and determined in the presence of large number of ions.

SEVERAL hydroxamic acids have been used for the complex formation studies with titanium by earlier workers¹⁻⁶. *N-m-tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA) has been used for the first time in this laboratory for extractive spectrophotometric determination of Nb(V)^{7,8} and Ti(IV)⁹. The present communication deals with the various aspects of Ti(IV)-TMBHA extraction studies in water-chloroform system.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents: Standard titanium solution was prepared from potassium titanyl oxalate (AR) and was standardized¹⁰.

The reagent (TMBHA) was synthesised as reported earlier¹¹. Fresh solutions of the reagent in chloroform were used.

A Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

General Procedure: An aliquot of titanium solution containing 80 μg of Ti(IV) was taken and to it added enough concentrated hydrochloric acid so as to make acid strength in the range 2.0-8.0M. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The solution was shaken with 10 ml of 0.007 M TMBHA in chloroform for 10 min. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance was measured at 330 nm, the wave length of maximum absorbance, against similarly processed reagent blank. Ti(IV) present was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Spectral Properties of the Complex: The spectra of the reagent and the complex showed maximum

absorbance at 255 nm ($\epsilon = 1.54 \times 10^4$) and 330 nm ($\epsilon = 6.8 \times 10^3$) respectively. The system obeys Beer's law within the concentration range of 1.0-8.0 μg of Ti(IV) per ml of chloroform. The effective working range from the Ringbom plot was found to be 2.5-6.5 μg of Ti(IV) per ml of chloroform. The Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 330 nm is 0.0070 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The complex is stable for about 30 hr.

Effect of Acid and Chloride ion Concentration: The extent of Ti(IV) extraction increases with the increase in the concentration of hydrochloric acid within the range of 2-8M. The effect of chloride ion concentration on extraction showed that the extent of extraction increases with the increase in the concentration of chloride ions within the range of 3.0-8.0M (maintained by $M_0\text{Cl}_2$) at fixed acidity (3.0M).

Effect of TMBHA Concentration: Titanium (40 μg) was extracted with different concentrations of reagent varying from 1.8×10^{-4} to 2.0×10^{-2} M. The quantitative extraction is possible with 7.0×10^{-2} M reagent and remains constant thereafter.

Effect of Solvents: Amongst the various non-aqueous solvents tried (benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, isoamyl alcohol, isobutanol), chloroform was found to be most efficient.

Time of Equilibrium: The aqueous phase was equilibrated from 1 to 30 min. The per cent extraction increases up to 5 min and remains constant thereafter. Hence, a time of 10 min was arbitrarily chosen for entire extraction studies.

Effect of Foreign Ions: Many foreign ions were tested for interferences. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion needed to cause $\pm 2\%$

error in the recovery of Ti(IV). Many ions are tolerable in moderate amounts whose tolerance limits are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF Ti(IV) : Ti(IV)=40 μ g, [TMBHA]=0.007M IN CHLOROFORM, HCl=8.0M, λ_{max} =330 nm.

Diverse ion	Added as	Tolerance limit, ion/Ti, w/w
Al ³⁺	Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .16H ₂ O	100
Cd ²⁺	3CdSO ₄ .8H ₂ O	125
Co ²⁺	CoSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	250
Cu ²⁺	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	50
Cr ³⁺	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	200
Ce ⁴⁺	Ce(SO ₄) ₃ .4H ₂ O	120
Fe ²⁺	Fe(NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	50
Fe ³⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ .Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .24H ₂ O	100
Hg ²⁺	HgCl ₂	175
Mn ²⁺	MnCl ₂ .4H ₂ O	400
Ni ²⁺	NiSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	400
Nb ⁵⁺	Nb ₂ O ₅	40
Ta ⁵⁺	Ta ₂ O ₅	100
Pd ²⁺	Pd(ClO ₄) ₂	70
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	75
Sn ²⁺	SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	20
UO ₂ ²⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	150
V ⁵⁺	V ₂ O ₅	50
VO ²⁺	VOSO ₄ .K ₂ O	400
Zn ²⁺	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	100
Zr ⁴⁺	Zr(SO ₄) ₂	400
Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ⁴⁻	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	50
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	25
PO ₄ ³⁻	H ₃ PO ₄	100
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .2H ₂ O	800
Cit ³⁻	Citric acid	1000
Tart ²⁻	Tartaric acid	1200
Br ⁻	K Br	500
I ⁻	KI	600
F ⁻	NH ₄ F	50
EDTA ⁴⁻	EDTA (disodium salt)	2000

The ions which interfere seriously are Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Sn²⁺, Fe²⁺, Nb⁵⁺, Cu²⁺ and F⁻. Tantalum can be tolerated in 100 times excess.

The absorbance obtained from eight determinations of 40 μ g of Ti(IV) was 0.570 \pm 0.005. The relative mean deviation and standard deviation has been found to be \pm 0.9% and \pm 1.4% respectively. The total operation requires 30 min. Thus, the method is simple, rapid, applicable at tracer concentrations and affords clear-cut separation of Ti(IV) from large number of ions.

Nature and Composition of the Extractable Species :

The fact that extraction is a function of chloride ion concentration shows the role of chloride ions in the formation of neutral extractable complex. A plot of log D_(Ti) versus log Cl at fixed acidity (3.0M) gave a slope of one which clearly indicates that only one chloride ion takes part in complexation.

A plot of log D_(Ti) versus log [TMBHA]_{org} (concentration of TMBHA in organic phase at equilibrium) at two different acid concentrations (3 and 8M HCl) gave a slope of two which indicates that titanium forms 1 : 2 complex with TMBHA. This composition was also supported by the Job's¹²

method as applied by Kabadi¹³ and slope ratio method¹⁴ when studied at two different acid concentrations (3 and 8 M HCl). The perusal of all these observations shows that the composition of the extractable neutral complex may be probably 1 : 1 : 2 with respect to Ti(IV), Cl and TMBHA. The extraction reaction therefore can be written as :

where, HR = TMBHA.

Thus, the probable extractable species in this system is TiOCl. R.HR, where HR may be associated through titanyl oxygen atom as suggested by earlier workers for analogous systems⁴

Metal-ligand Stability Constants : The conditional metal-ligand stepwise stability constants of the extracted complex were computed from the spectrophotometric data by Yatsimirskii's^{15,16} and Leden's¹⁷ methods. Suitable functions were constructed in terms of intercepts obtained at zero-ligand concentration. The equilibrium ligand concentration was calculated from Beer's law data considering full complexation (1 : 2 in present case) of metal ion with the reagent at studied reagent concentrations¹⁸.

The log K₁ and log K₂ values of the complex are found to be 3.67 and 3.32 by Yatsimirskii's method and those by Leden's method are 3.54 and 3.20 respectively. The respective values of log β_2 comes out to be 6.99 and 6.74 by two methods.

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